

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

GLOBAL CLIMATE CHALLENGES - ELEMENTS OF MITIGATION MEASURES FOR SUSTAINABLE PRODUCTION OF GEORGIAN FRUITS

Z. Bobokashvili

PhD, Associate Professor

E. Maghlakelidze

PhD Scientific and Research Center of Agriculture

Fruit Research Service

V. KvaliaSvili

Academician of Academy of Agriculture, Doctor of Agricultural Sciences

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Abstract

Global climate changes are leading to an increase in scarce marginal land areas worldwide, intensification of the desertification process, a significant shortage of irrigation water, and a permanent increase in erosion processes. These issues are also noticeable in Georgia, especially in its eastern part, where negative dynamics of agroclimatic indicators can be observed, such as temperature increases, uneven precipitation distribution, and decreased intensity.

Therefore, for the sustainable development of the fruit-growing sector in Georgia, it is crucial to diversify production and select promising varieties that exhibit high adaptability to the changing climate conditions.

Keywords: climate, fruit, temperature, warming.

It is well-known that global climate changes, amidst long-standing conflicting scientific and public discussions, have gradually become a daily reality. Climate change has unpredictable effects on global agricultural production and the world market. No country is immune to this problem. One of the international forums dedicated to climate change adopted the slogan: "Climate change has no borders." Indeed, international and local scientific studies, observations of current climate indices, and virtual models of future climate predictions clearly and reliably confirm that significant climate changes will occur worldwide in the future (2022-2070 and 2071-2100). The future climate change scenario is likely to feature numerous negative aspects, alongside a few fragmented positive ones.

These fluctuations will manifest not only as an inexorable increase in the average air temperature but also as irreversible changes in other agro-climatic and ecological factors caused by this event (*WMO Guidelines on the Calculation of Climate Normals*)

In the 20th century, the global average air temperature increased by 0.6°C (<http://www.ipcc.ch/>). This process is irreversible and will likely increase the average global temperature by 2-4.5°C in the 21st century (*Pachauri et al., 2014; Bruinsma, J. (2003)*). Climate change has led to an increase in impoverished marginal land areas, intensified desertification, significant irrigation water shortages, and a permanent rise in erosion processes (Climate Change: The Scientific Assessment Report of the IPCC 2018)

These processes are also noticeable in Georgia (Meladze M. and Meladze G., 2015; The Third National Communication Climate Change of Georgia, 2015. UNDP).

Expected climatic risks in Georgia will particularly affect agricultural industrial regions. It has been revealed that drought periods are expected to lengthen,

cycles of high-temperature days (+32-35°C and higher) will extend, solar radiation intensity will increase, rainfall will be unevenly distributed and reduced, and unfavorable meteorological events (late spring frosts, hail, etc.) will become more frequent. Additionally, the snow cover period will shorten, the incidence of hot winds will rise, new pathogens will appear and increase in number, water shortages and lower groundwater levels will occur, and the CO₂ concentration in the air will increase (*The Third National Communication Climate Change of Georgia, 2015. UNDP; Gunia G., 2019; Elizbarashvili M et al.2017*).

This unequivocally confirms that Georgia's fruit production sector, as well as the country's agriculture as a whole, faces significant challenges. Therefore, to mitigate the impact of climate change, it is crucial to take stock, develop appropriate targeted measures, and be ready for their implementation.

The degree of vulnerability to climate change is particularly high in the eastern region of Georgia, where the trend of a sharp temperature increase is the most noticeable among climatic anomalies (Tavartkiladze et al., 2012). By 2100, the predicted changes in climatic elements (a temperature increase of +4.2°C and a 10-20% decrease in annual precipitation) will lead to significant aridization and associated desertification risks. This trend will pose a great danger to the agricultural sector of Eastern Georgia, including the well-developed fruit-growing industry in the region (*Meladze G. and Meladze M., 2020*). High temperatures will alter the phenotypic, morphological, physiological, and productivity indicators of the varieties.

In relation to global climate challenges, Georgian fruit growers often ask the following questions: How real is the expected negative effect in Georgia? What kind of risks can we expect in orchards? And what can we do in the short and long term?

Climate change may cause a number of negative events in the fruit production sector:

- Significant increase in irrigation water consumption, leading to water deficits in orchards
- Heating and burning of the fruit surface, resulting in a loss of the fruit's marketable qualities
- Thermal injury to leaves, reducing their assimilation activity and negatively affecting yield
- Negative changes in the adaptability of cultivated fruit tree varieties, causing sharp changes in the qualitative and quantitative characteristics of the harvest and increasing annual variability
- Increased intensity and speed of the spread of harmful pathogens
- Reduced effectiveness of flower pollination
- Negative changes in the physiological, morphological, and biochemical properties of fruits, including less carbohydrate accumulation, decreased taste quality, and reduced storage capacity
- Deterioration of fruit coloring and reduction of anthocyanins and phenols due to decreased day-night temperature amplitude
- In some regions of Georgia, a decrease in winter chilling temperatures (CU) leading to reduced flowering intensity
- Early onset of flowering and changes in the harvest period
- Limitation of agricultural activities in orchards during hot days, negatively affecting the working schedule

To mitigate the negative impact of the probable risks and maintain productivity and stable incomes from orchards, it is important to consider the following proposed elements of adaptive measures:

- Arrangement of drip irrigation in fruit orchards in regions of Western Georgia that currently receive more rainfall, such as Guria, Samegrelo, and Adjara.
- Targeted spraying of special preparations to protect against heat and ultraviolet rays, including the use of plant-based phytostimulants containing calcium, kaolin, other similar phyllosilicates, and preparations made from cellulose nanocrystals.
- Use of modern sensors and dendrometers in gardens with drip irrigation to monitor soil, air, and fruit conditions. This includes smart taps and other means to maintain optimal soil moisture and ensure precise irrigation, thus conserving water.
- Adjustment of pesticide and agrochemical application periods, preferably transferring spraying to the evening and morning hours.
- Use of resource-saving conservative principles in the garden, such as green cover between rows of fruit trees to protect the soil from overheating.
- Intensive use of forecasting methods for the spread of harmful pathogens, like pheromone monitoring and phenological models, for optimal prevention.
- Targeted arrangement of shading and anti-hail nets in gardens.
- Use of Regulated Deficit Irrigation (RDI) approaches.

- Emphasis on arranging windbreaks, not only to contain strong winds but also to reduce the negative impact of hot winds.

- Selection of adaptive drought-resistant fruit tree crops, and highly plastic varieties and rootstocks.
- Installation of real and virtual agrometeorological stations for accurate reflection of the hydrothermal regime in the agrobiocenoses of gardens. Based on this, appropriate irrigation schemes should be specified.
- Using rainwater harvesting and other progressive water-saving irrigation methods to ensure consistent irrigation in water-scarce conditions.
- Use of mulching technologies, employing organic and plastic mulch to retain moisture.
- Detailed investigation of the micro-region before planting orchards, considering soil and climatic conditions as well as current and future irrigation water regimes.
- Arrangement of dynamic (mobile) agrosolar systems in orchards to protect plants from the sun and produce "green" electricity for agricultural use.
- Focusing on relatively drought-resistant fruit crops in conditions with questionable irrigation water supply, such as pistachios, rapeseeds, and olives.

To mitigate the effects of climate change, the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) has developed the concept of sustainable agricultural production, which involves the adaptation of agricultural systems in response to climate change (<http://www.fao.org/sustainability/frameworks-approaches>).

At the modern stage of fruit growing, increasing fruit harvests and improving product quality require diversifying agricultural production. This implies selecting new varieties that exhibit high adaptability to marginal, desertified, and eroded lands. An important direction for improving the varietal assortment of fruit trees is the introduction of new, high-marketing varieties of foreign selection and their comprehensive study. Preliminary assessment of new varieties should be based on research conducted in the ecological conditions of the origin country of the genotype and should consider local soil-climatic features (*Fruits of Georgia (catalog), 2001*).

Testing new genotypes of fruit trees, evaluating their biological and economic potential under different soil-climatic conditions, and selection will promote biodiversity as one of the climate mitigation strategies. This will also create the foundation for sustainable production in the agricultural sector. According to FAO data, in the last century, 50% of the increase in agricultural production was due to plant selection, with the remainder coming from technological process improvements (Faostat, 2020: <http://faostat.fao.org/default.aspx>; *Keggenhoff, et al.*). In the near future, the purpose of selective research in terms of food safety will become even more crucial. Therefore, selecting new plant genotypes and evaluating their sustainability in local environmental conditions is very important. (*Agrobiodiversity of Georgia (2015); Geostat (2021)*).

It is significant that fruit farmers clearly understand and consider that global climate challenges are becoming a constant part of our lives. The risks posed

by these changes, with reasonable planning and implementation of relevant measures, are fully manageable. Based on this, it is quite possible to achieve a high-quality, competitive, and highly productive fruit harvest, ensuring the economic sustainability of those employed in the fruit-growing sector.

Our scientific research center's fruit growing service aims at the agronomic, commercial, and physiological development of leading fruit crops—apples, pears, peaches, and berries—in the regions of Eastern Georgia, which have diverse soil and climatic conditions: Kakheti, Shida Kartli, and Samtskhe-Javakheti. This is being done under conditions altered by climate change. We assess the potential under increasing average temperatures by conducting multidisciplinary pomological and ecophysiological studies. Additionally, we aim to determine common phenological regularities to predict and modify harvest periods for fruit production in Eastern Georgia. We collect complex data on the biological and agronomic indicators of various varieties, sorting and recommending ecologically plastic and agronomically valuable varieties based on this data.

The reasonable selection of fruit and crop varieties resistant to temperature stress for cultivation in relevant territories, along with various corrective factors to optimize plant life processes in unfavorable environmental conditions, are important tasks facing physiologists. Successfully addressing these tasks will contribute to the stable production of fruit products. (Doroshenko T

For accurate diagnostics of heat resistance in fruits, a set of physiological and biochemical parameters that objectively reflect the functional state of the plant organism under different temperature stressors should be used. Their application is very promising for selecting the best assortments. This issue will persist due to the continuous appearance of new varieties of fruit crops in the domestic market, which attract producers and consumers with their economically valuable traits and properties. An objective assessment of these traits must be conducted. (*Doroshenko T. et al*)

A deeper study of the heat resistance of perennial plants allows for the development of a number of innovative techniques, such as the use of foliar micro- and macro elements, which activate metabolic processes and ultimately ensure the stability of the industry under varying weather conditions year after year.

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